

Evaluation of conservation methods for archaeological wet wood with structured light 3D scanning and μ -CT

Ingrid Stelzner*

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
ingrid.stelzner@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Jörg Stelzner

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
joerg.stelzner@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

*Corresponding author

Jorge Martinez-Garcia

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences
and Arts - School of Engineering and
Architecture, Horw, Switzerland
jorge.martinezgarcia@hslu.ch
www.hslu.ch/TES

Damian Gwerder

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences
and Arts - School of Engineering and
Architecture, Horw, Switzerland
damian.gwerder.01@hslu.ch
www.hslu.ch/TES

Markus Wittköpper

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
markus.wittkoepper@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Waldemar Muskalla

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
waldemar.muskalla@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Anja Cramer

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
anja.cramer@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Guido Heinz

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
guido.heinz@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Markus Egg

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie
Mainz, Germany
markus.egg@rgzm.de
www.rgzm.de

Philipp Schuetz

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences
and Arts - School of Engineering and
Architecture, Horw, Switzerland
philipp.schuetz@hslu.ch
www.hslu.ch/TES

Abstract

The conservation of wooden cultural heritage from wet sites is challenging. Depending on its degree of degradation, waterlogged archaeological wood will collapse, shrink and distort upon drying. Besides damage in the surface, the structure itself is damaged leading to destabilisation or a completely damaged object. Conservation measures are a prerequisite for the preservation of the find material. The various conservation methods available can prevent this damage, but in some cases only up to a certain degree. The evaluation of the conservation methods is usually limited to the surface of the object. Invasive methods, such as the examination of core holes under the microscope, provide information about the structure of the sample, but only a small area of the sample can be examined with preparative effort. In this study, we aimed to analyse both the three-dimensional changes and the inner structure of the conserved wooden samples. Therefore, we used structured-light 3D-Scans before and after conservation and micro-computed tomography (μ CT) after conservation. The samples were conserved with some of the most common conservation methods:

besides the alcohol-ether-resin method, the conservation methods by impregnation with melamin-formaldehyde (Kauramin 800), lactitol/trehalose, saccharose and silicone oil were investigated. In addition, different polyethylene glycol (PEG) treatments with subsequent freeze-drying were also investigated: one-stage with PEG 2000, two-stage with PEG 400 and PEG 4000 and three-stage with PEG 400, PEG 1500 and PEG 4000. On the basis of the data we analysed and classified the damage patterns in the conserved samples according to a catalogue. These were shrinkage, collapse and cracks. The best results were obtained by the conservation methods using PEG and freeze-drying, alcohol-ether-resin method as well as Kauramin 800. This evaluation showed the respective disadvantages of the individual conservation methods. These damages provide indications for the further development of the methods.

Keywords: conservation, waterlogged wood, volume, shrinkage, rating system, computed tomography, structured-light 3D scanning

Introduction

The conservation of wooden cultural heritage from wet sites is challenging. Depending on its degree of degradation, waterlogged archaeological wood (WAW) will collapse, shrink and distort upon drying. Besides damage in the surface, the structure itself is damaged leading to destabilisation or a completely damaged object. The main damage patterns are shrinkage, collapse and cracks. Conservation measures are a prerequisite for the preservation of the find material. WAW stabilisation and comparative studies of conservation methods have been done since the beginning of wood conservation (Bräker et al. 1979, Grattan 1987). The various conservation methods available can prevent this damage, but in some cases only up to a certain degree. In particular, the extent of shrinkage has been used to assess methods by comparing the dimensions before and after conservation (e.g. Babiński 2015, Bräker et al. 1979, Broda et al. 2021, Broda and Mazela 2017, Christensen 1971, Grattan 1982; Hoffmann 2009, Imazu et al. 2016, Majka et al. 2018, Nguyen 2018, Nguyen et al. 2018, Schindelholz et al. 2009, Stelzner 2018, 2017, Stelzner et al. 2022, Vetter et al. 2010, Wittköpper et al. 2016, 'www.rgzm.de/kur', 2022). However, the evaluation has usually been limited to the surface of the object. Invasive methods, such as the examination of core samples under the microscope, provide information about the structure of the sample and the conservation agent, but only a small area of the sample can be examined with some preparative effort (e.g. Jensen et al. 2002, Schmitt and Noldt 1993, Stelzner 2017). A systematic evaluation and comparison of conservation methods considering the three-dimensional inner structures is missing for most of the methods. First attempts at considering the inner structure of conserved wood was done by Stelzner et al. (2022) where the dimensional changes of conserved wood were evaluated. In this study the aim is to quantify systematically the damage patterns like cracks, collapse and shrinkage of the samples using a criteria-based rating system in order to evaluate the success of the conservation methods.

Material and methods

Samples

The basis of this study is a reference collection of conserved archaeological wood at the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäol-

ogie, Mainz, Germany. This collection was built up throughout a research project that was performed from 2008 to 2011 (Wittköpper et al. 2016, 'www.rgzm.de/kur', 2022). The samples encompassed archaeological objects that were collected from multiple sites. The objects were made of different types of wood and have different degrees of degradation. The objects were divided into smaller samples. Five samples were assigned to each group, which were conserved in the test series with one of the methods. The degree of degradation was determined by the maximum water content (U_{max}) (Hoffmann 2013, Schniewind 1990) which was analysed destructively for the control samples to be air-dried, and non-destructively for the samples to be conserved (Cook and Grattan 1991). After documenting the condition of approximately 800 samples, they were conserved with the most established methods from specialised institutions according to their standard methods (Table 1). A detailed overview of the project, the conservation methods and the samples is given on the project homepage ('www.rgzm.de/kur', 2022).

In this study, the ten largest test series were selected in order to cover a high variety of methods and wood species. Sample series of different wood genus were investigated: three from oak (*Quercus*), two from fir (*Abies*) and one each from alder (*Alnus*), ash (*Fraxinus*), beech (*Fagus*), pine (*Pinus*) and spruce (*Picea*). Overall, 83 samples were analysed (Table 1). Figure 1 gives an overview of the sampling and measurement methods of this research.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the experimental procedure: sampling, conservation, measurements with structured-light 3D scanning and μ CT

Table 1. Overview of conservation methods.

Conservation method	Institutions and short descriptions of the methods
Alcohol-ether-resin (AIEt)	<p>Institution: Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum, Zürich, Switzerland.</p> <p>Treatment: Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection 3 % Paraloid B72 solution in acetone.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: 70.7 % diethyl ether, 16.1 % dammar resin, 6.4 % rosin, 3.2 % dienol D102, 3.2 % rhizinus oil, 0.4 % PEG 400</p> <p>Number of samples: 8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)</p>
Kauramin 800 (K800)	<p>Institution: Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany</p> <p>Treatment: Bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polymerisation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60 °C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: 25 % Kauramin 800 solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol)</p> <p>Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)</p>
lactitol- trehalose (LaTr)	<p>Institution: Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany</p> <p>Treatment: Starting with 30 % concentration. Increasing monthly in 10 % steps up to 70 %. Bath temperature 55 °C. After removal from the bath, the surfaces were dusted with crystalline lactitol monohydrate and dried in a heating oven over a period of one week. After drying, the surface was cleaned by dabbing with damp cloths.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: lactitol-trehalose solution (9:1) 30 % – 70 %. Addition of biocide if necessary (0.1 % Bioban 404)</p> <p>Number of samples: 7 (alder, beech, fir, oak (2), pine, spruce)</p>
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying (PEG1)	<p>Institution: Nationalmuseet, Copenhagen, Denmark</p> <p>Treatment: Starting with 10 % PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40 % at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25 % PEG 2000 solution in ethanol.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: PEG 2000, 10 – 40 % solution with tap water</p> <p>Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)</p>
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying (PEG2)	<p>Institution: Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany</p> <p>Treatment: Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 5 % PEG 400 solution. Raising the concentration in 5 % steps. At its calculated final concentration, it was kept constant. Then the increase of PEG 4000 solution was continued in 5 % steps up to its final concentration. Precooling of the wood to 5 °C then deep-freezing to -25 to -35 °C, freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C).</p> <p>Impregnation solution: PEG-solution in demineralised water (PEG 400 and PEG 4000) was adapted according to the condition of the wood (PEGcon)</p> <p>Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)</p>
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying (PEG3)	<p>Institution: Archäologische Staatssammlung, Munich, Germany</p> <p>Treatment: Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 11 % increasing to 15 % PEG 400 solution at room temperature. 16 % increasing to 20.5 % PEG 1500 solution at 40 °C. 20.5 % increasing to 27.5 % PEG 4000 solution at 40 °C. Washing of the wood and wrapping in cellulose tissues. Intermediate storage in freezer (-25 to -35 °C) until freeze-drying. Subsequent freeze-drying in a cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C). Excess of PEG was removed with a brush and ethanol.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: PEG-solution in demineralised water: 15 % PEG 400, 20.5 % PEG 1500, 27.5 % PEG 4000</p> <p>Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)</p>
Sucrose (Sac)	<p>Institution: Sächsisches Landesamt für Archäologie, Dresden, Germany</p> <p>Treatment: Concentrated the solution in 10 % steps, from 10 % up to 60 % sugar solution at room temperature. Slow, controlled air-drying in microperforated bags. Removal of crystallised sugar residues from the surface with damp sponge.</p> <p>Impregnation solution: Aqueous sucrose solution 10 % – 60 %. If necessary biocide addition composed of 0.6 %, sodium benzoate (E211), 0.5 % Parmetol K40, 0.5 % Quartasept Plus and 0.02 % Tallofin OT</p> <p>Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)</p>
Silicone oil (Sil)	<p>Institution: Texas University, Texas, USA</p> <p>Treatment: Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with acetone. Placing the still dripping wet acetone-impregnated samples in impregnation solution under normal atmospheric conditions. Triggering the polymerisation of the impregnation solution by gaseous catalyst: DBTDA (dibutyl diacetate).</p> <p>Impregnation solution: 80 % silicone oil (SFD1 (66 %) + SFD5 (34 %) - silanol functional polydimethylsiloxanes "PDMS") and 20 % crosslinker MTMS (methyltrimethoxysilane)</p> <p>Number of samples: 8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)</p>

3D-scan

From 2008 onwards, the wet samples were captured before conservation and in dry condition after conservation using a structured-light 3D-scanner. A structured-light 3D scanner is a sensor that consists of cameras and light projection. It is an optical method for capturing 3D data on the visible surface. The capturing device was an ATOS III Rev. 01 scanner from GOM (a ZEISS company) with a field of view of 500 mm \times 500 mm \times 500 mm and a point distance of 0.25 mm (Wittkopper et al. 2016). After data capture, all scans were processed in the ATOS Version v6.2 Software using similar parameters by employing Python scripts to control the workflow and obtain a reduced 3D mesh with a closed surface. To analyse volume changes after ten years the conserved samples were captured again in 2020. Since the same sensor was no longer available, a successor model was used. The ATOS III Rev.02 Triple Scan from GOM (a ZEISS company) with a field of view of 320 mm \times 240 mm \times 240 mm and a point distance of 0.10 mm was used. The processing of scans results in 3D meshes of the samples.

μ CT analyses

Analysis of the condition of the wood structure inside the samples about ten years after their conservation was carried out at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts with a μ CT-system. The tomographic analysis was performed on the in-house laboratory XCT system (Diondo d2, Germany). An optimised setup and acquisition protocol for the μ CT measurements was developed for conserved wood. The measurements were conducted by setting the X-ray source (XWT-225 TCHE+ from X-ray works, Garbsen, Germany) in high power mode and choosing an operation voltage of 120 kV and a filament current of 167 μ A with a 1 mm aluminium filter. The wood samples were mounted in a sample holder and placed in the sample chamber. The sample was rotated 360 $^\circ$ in continuous mode during the acquisition. The radiographical projections were recorded with a 4343 DX-I X-ray detector (Varex, Salt Lake City, U.S.A.), with a pixel size of 139 μ m. The distance between the X-ray source and the sample was between 160 and 250 mm and the distance between the X-ray source and the detector was 860 mm, giving a magnification between 3.4 and 5.4 and a nominal voxel size between 27 and 44 μ m. A total of 3000

projection images were acquired during the sample rotation of 360 $^\circ$. The resulting projections were converted into a 3D image stack of approx. 3000 \times 3000 \times 3000 voxels using the CERA reconstruction software based on the filtered back projection Feldkamp algorithm (Feldkamp et al. 1984) from Siemens. The achieved resolution of the μ CT measurements depends on the size of the samples (Stelzner and Million 2015). Image cross-sections and 3D renderings of the wood were visualised in VGStudioMax3.4 software. Also, in order to obtain the values of the wood volume concerning inner cracks and collapse, the surface determination of the very inhomogeneous material was done manually for each sample with the different segmentation tools of the software. Afterwards the surface and volume values of the segmented μ CT data and that of the structured-light 3D scanning were calculated with the same software.

Rating system criteria

To evaluate the data of the structured-light 3D-scanning and μ CT, a rating system was established to assess dimensional changes, collapse and cracks. This rating system was inspired by other evaluation procedures of conservation methods (Suenson-Taylor 2001, Suenson-Taylor et al. 1999, Sully and Suenson-Taylor 1996 and Stelzner et al. 2022). Table 2 presents the criteria and the samples rating system. In order to evaluate the volume changes in the measurement, data from structured-light 3D scanning was used to calculate the shrinkage (S) from the volume of the samples before (V_{wet}) and after (V_{dry}) conservation (Rowell and Youngs 1981, Stamm 1959, Stamm et al. 1955, Stamm and Tarkow 1947):

$$S (I) = \frac{V_{wet} - V_{dry}}{V_{wet}} \times 100 \quad [\%] \quad [2]$$

The evaluation of the conservation methods was done by determining the dimensional stability on the basis of the volume data that was derived from the surface of the whole sample. The values of the individual wood anatomical directions can be taken from the database ('www.rgzm.de/kur', 2022).

Furthermore, the dimensional changes of the inner structures were calculated from the volumes of the structured-light 3D scans and μ CT data. The volumes were taken from measurements which were carried out in 2020, approximately ten years after conservation. The difference

Table 2. Criteria based rating system.

	Maximum	Greater	Several	Few	Minor	Minimal
Condition score	1	2	3	4	5	6
Cell collapse: cell collapse on the sample is qualitatively and quantitatively considered. Quantification of the collapsed area per sample volume						
outer areas	Collapse damage extensive over whole area	Collapse damage extensive over greater part of the object	Several areas of damage through cell collapse	Isolated areas of collapse, not extensive	Minor areas of damage through cell collapse	Sample intact, no cell collapse
inner areas	Collapse damage extensive over whole area	Collapse damage extensive over greater part of the object	Several areas of damage through cell collapse	Isolated areas of collapse, not extensive	Minor areas of damage through cell collapse	Sample intact, no cell collapse
Cracks per area: Transverse and longitudinal (along the fibres) cracks regarding to their number and size are assessed						
Transverse cracks						
maximum width	> 2 mm	1-2 mm	0.5-1 mm	0.2-0.5 mm	0.1-0.2 mm	< 0.1 mm
maximum length	> 100 mm	bis 100 mm	bis 70 mm	bis 50 mm	bis 20 mm	< 10 mm
quantification	A great many cracks	Many cracks	Several cracks	Few cracks	Minor areas with cracks	No cracks
Longitudinal cracks						
maximum width	> 2 mm	1-2 mm	0.5-1 mm	0.2-0.5 mm	0.1-0.2 mm	< 0.1 mm
maximum length	> 100 mm	bis 100 mm	bis 70 mm	bis 50 mm	bis 20 mm	< 10 mm
quantification	A great many cracks	Many cracks	Several cracks	Few cracks	Minor areas with cracks	No cracks
Volume stability: Volume and shrinkage is calculated on the basis of structured-light 3D Scans and μ CT data						
Shrinkage of the entire sample (S I)	>15%	12-14%	9-11%	6-8%	3-5%	0-2%
Shrinkage of the inner volume (S II)	>10%	8-9%	6-7%	4-5%	2-3%	0-1%

between the volume of the outer surface of the sample that is derived from the structured-light 3D scans and the volume of the μ CT data, where the inner structure is considered, describe the volume of the voids. The volume of the voids was set in relation to the volume of the outer surface of the sample (Stelzner et al. 2022):

$$S(II) = \frac{V_{Scan} - V_{\mu CT}}{V_{Scan}} \times 100 \quad [\%] \quad [3]$$

Cell collapse on the sample was qualitatively and quantitatively recorded. Thereby the outer areas (with connection to the surface) are considered as well as the inner areas. The occurrence of cracks is surveyed, but here a distinction is made between the transverse direction and the longitudinal direction (along the fibres). Both the number and the size of the cracks are recorded and quantified. The sizes of the

cracks were measured with VGStudioMax3.4 in the μ CT data.

After recording the results, they were categorised with values going from 1 (poor results) to 6, (very good outcomes) (Table 2). The condition score was calculated as a sum of each individual categories: dimensional stability, collapse and cracks. The results of individual samples were grouped by conservation method and the average condition score of each method was calculated.

Results and discussion

Dimensional stability

The shrinkage of the whole sample S(I), % was calculated from the data of the structured-light 3D Scans before (Scan 1) and after conservation (Scan 2). The shrinkage

S(II), % of the inner volume was calculated from the data of both structured-light 3D Scans (Scan 3) and μ CT data ten years after conservation (Figure 1). The values were categorised according to Table 2 resulting in a condition score for each sample in terms of shrinkage of the inner volume and of the whole sample. The mean value of the condition score was calculated for each conservation method (Figure 2). Regarding overall shrinkage, the lowest score was achieved by the air-dried samples meaning that the air-dried samples reveal the highest shrinkage. The lowest shrinkage which means the highest condition score was achieved by PEG (1) followed by melamin-formaldehyde (Kauramin 800), PEG (2) and PEG (3). The alcohol-ether-resin method achieved moderate results in volume stabilisation. The results of the lactitol/trehalose and saccharose followed. The least result was achieved by the silicone oil treated samples which had a higher shrinkage.

The samples with the least inner shrinkage were the samples treated with alcohol-ether-resin (Figure 3a). The PEG treated samples (PEG (1), PEG (2) and PEG (3)) had also minimal shrinkage. They were followed by saccharose and Kauramin 800, which showed, in part, rather large cracks. Among the conserved samples, those treated with silicone oil and the lactitol/trehalose ones (Figure 3b) revealed most inner shrinkage. Overall, the untreated wooden samples showed most defects which is reflected in the lowest condition score.

Cell collapse

Cell collapse is caused by the development of capillary forces upon drying (Hawley 1931). In the μ CT images, collapsed areas are mostly visible as spindle-shaped cracks, in the radial direction, getting wider in the middle (Figure 5a, b). Here, the extent of cell collapse considered in the outer area and in the centre of the sample per sample volume. The condition score for each sample was taken and the mean condition score was calculated according to the rating system (Table 2).

Overall, the values obtained are very comparable whether the collapse happened within the structure or in the outer area, close to the surface (Figure 4). The most collapse appeared in the untreated reference samples revealing the lowest condition score followed by the treatment with lactitol/trehalose (Figure 5a) and the saccharose (Figure 5b)

Figure 2. Condition of the samples is expressed by the mean value of the condition score of differences in volumes before and after conservation and drawn in dependence of the conservation treatment.

Figure 3a and b. μ CT 3D-visualisation of the inner cavities (yellow parts) of an oak sample conserved with (a) alcohol-ether resin and (b) lactitol/trehalose.

Figure 4. Condition of the samples expressed by the mean value of the condition score of collapse per conservation treatment.

treatment. The silicone oil treated samples show medium values followed by the samples treated with PEG (3), Kauramin 800, PEG (2) and the alcohol-ether-resin method. The samples conserved with PEG (1) have the lowest values in terms of collapse.

Cracks

In the μ CT data, cracks in longitudinal and transverse direction were visible. These cracks were assessed by size and amount. According to the rating system (Table 2) the values were categorised and the mean condition score was calculated for each method.

The samples with the highest condition score show the best results regarding cracks in the inner structure (Figure 6). The samples with the fewest cracks in the longitudinal direction are the alcohol-ether-resin method and the saccharose method followed by the samples treated with PEG (2), lactitol-trehalose and Kauramin 800 (Figure 7a). The samples that were conserved with PEG (1) (Figure 7b) had the most cracks compared to the samples treated with PEG (3) and silicone oil which achieved better results. However, the untreated samples had the lowest condition score.

All samples showed more or less cracks transversally. The samples with the best condition score in this category were treated with lactitol/trehalose, alcohol-ether-resin method, PEG (2), silicone oil and saccharose before Kauramin 800, PEG (1) and PEG (3). The air-dried sample showed the lowest condition score. In a few cases treated with Kauramin 800, big splits especially between the highly degraded outer areas and the well-preserved inner areas were observed (Figure 7a). Notably, the samples treated with PEG (1) showed many fine cracks in all directions (Figure 7b).

Summary

Figure 8 provides an overview of all values achieved in the three damage categories: shrinkage, cracks and collapse, with the average values of each category being further averaged. In summary, the untreated samples had the lowest condition score values in all categories. Among the conserved samples, the ones treated with lactitol/trehalose have the lowest values meaning they have the highest amount of damage, particularly in terms of collapse and cracks. Silicone oil and saccharose treatment have the

Figure 5a and b. μ CT cross section of an alder sample treated with (a) lactitol/trehalose and (b) saccharose showing cell collapse in the wood structure.

Figure 6. Condition of the samples is expressed by the mean condition score of cracks in transversal and longitudinal directions and drawn in dependence of the conservation treatment.

Figure 7a and b. μ CT cross section of (a) an oak sample treated with Kauramin 800 with a large crack and (b) an ash sample treated with PEG 2000 followed by freeze-drying showing cracks in the wood structure.

second lowest values. The main damage of the saccharose treated samples is collapse whereas cracks and shrinkage are moderate. Silicone oil treated samples have low rates in volume stability, more cracks and a moderate rate in the category collapse.

The Kauramin 800 treated samples achieved high values in all categories, but the rates in volume stability decreased due to a few big splits. There were also more cracks visible in the samples resulting in a lower score. The samples treated with the alcohol-ether-resin method achieved very high results

Figure 8. Condition of the samples is expressed by the mean condition score of collapse, cracks and shrinkage that was added up and drawn in dependence of the conservation treatment.

in the condition rate in all categories. The PEG treatments achieved also very high rates, with PEG (1) having the highest condition score followed by PEG (2) and PEG (3). But the PEG (1) treated samples showed many cracks, as well as the PEG (3) samples. The samples with PEG (2) had less cracks but more collapse, as well as PEG (3) compared to PEG (1).

Whether the type of wood has an influence on conservation could not be clarified here. However, the influence of the condition on the conservation result could be observed (Stelzner et al. 2022). According to this, lightly degraded WAW is more difficult to stabilise than heavily degraded WAW.

Conclusion

In this comparative study 83 samples previously conserved with eight different methods were investigated. For the first time, data derived from structured-light 3D scans and μ CT were systematically analysed using a criteria-based rating system. With structured-light 3D scans the shrinkage of the samples was measured. The μ CT data from the inner structure of the samples allowed quantification of collapse and cracks. The damage patterns were identified as shrinkage, collapse and cracks and recorded in the digital data. Quantification was made on the basis of a catalogue of criteria. Overall, silicone oil, lactitol/trehalose and saccharose were not as successful as PEG impregnation methods followed by freeze-drying, Kauramin 800 and alcohol-ether-resin showing higher mean condition scores. The inner structure of conserved archaeological wood

reveals several degradation patterns which are specific for each method. On this basis, a conclusion about the conservation methods was made. The samples were conserved by specialised laboratories and very experienced colleagues. In some cases, the duration of impregnation varied which was due to the time constraints of the project and might have an influence on the results. On the other hand, precisely these damage patterns also give an indication for the further development of the methods. One approach, for example, would be to modify the conservation method with polyethylene glycol 2000 and freeze-drying in such a way that fewer cracks occur that destabilise the object. This could be achieved, for example, by faster freezing or the addition of cryoprotectors.

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